

Luofu Shan

also known as “Mount Luofu”, “Loh Fau Mountain”, “Lo-feou Chan”

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Entry tags: Sacred mountain, Confucian (rujia 儒家) Traditions, Dongtian fudi, Guangdong, Religious Group, Chinese Buddhism, A Hybrid of Popular Beliefs, Ancestral Worship, Ritual centre, Mortuary shrine, Shrine, Cave or Cavern, Temple Buildings and Temple Cult, Religious Complex, Celestial Master (天師道), Tomb, Cemetery, Lingbao (Numinous Treasure), Indigenous Theology, Self-Cultivation, Confucianism, Hermits, Sacred Territory, Sacred Land, Quanzhen, Language, Daoism, Religious Practice, Religious Place, Early Chinese cosmogony, Peak Sanctuaries, Temple, Asceticism, Early Chinese Traditions, Altar, China, Monastery, Hill, Neo-Confucian, Cantonese, Chinese Religion, Orthodoxy, Chinese Folk Religions

Known as the “Grand Mountain of the Yue Region (粵岳)” according to the Han dynasty historian Sima Qian 司馬遷, Mount Luofu 羅浮山 held great significance as a cultural hub in southern China. It was also revered as one of the foremost mountains in Chinese history and culture due to the rich history of a significant number of practitioners of Daoism and Buddhism, as well as Confucian scholars who lived, studied, taught, and practiced their doctrines there. During its heyday, Mount Luofu was recorded as a thriving center of “Nine Taoist Temples, Eighteen Buddhist Temples, and Twenty-two Hermitages (九觀十八寺二十二庵)”. The name of Mount Luofu has many legendary origins, with the most renowned myth recounting a tale from the immortal Penglai Mountain 蓬萊 where a peak named “Fu Mountain (浮山)” resided. It was said that during the era of Emperor Yao, a period marred by widespread land inundation, the “Fu Mountain” from the sea drifted to the Lingnan region, where it collided with the pre-existing “Luo Mountain (羅山)” and merged to become Mount Luofu. Geographically, Mount Luofu is situated in the northwest of Boluo County 博羅縣, Huizhou City 惠州市, Guangdong Province 廣東省, China. With a total area exceeding 260 square kilometers, its principal peak, Feiyun Peak 飛雲頂, stands at an elevation of 1,296 meters. Mount Luofu is renowned for its unique rock formations, majestic waterfalls, mystical caves, abundant rainfall, and lush vegetation, making it an ideal site for spiritual retreats, alchemical practices, and health cultivation among Daoist and Buddhist practitioners, scholars, literati, and common people throughout history. According to historical records, as early as the Qin and Han dynasties, figures such as Zhu Lingzhi 朱靈芝, Ren Dun 任敦, and Liang Lu 梁廬, among others, were captivated by the scenic beauty of Mount Luofu and delved into its mountains to pursue Daoist practices. During the Xianhe period 咸和 of the Eastern Jin dynasty, Ge Hong 葛洪, one of the most important and famous Daoist practitioners and theorists, settled on Mount Luofu to engage in alchemical pursuits and established four Daoist temples: Baihe Temple 白鶴觀, Chongxu Temple 衝虛觀, Huanglong Temple 黃龍觀, and Sulao Temple 酥醪觀, recruiting disciples and conducting Daoist teachings. His wife, Baogu 鮑姑, and numerous disciples, including Teng Sheng 騰升, An Haijun 安海君, and Huang Yeren 黃野人 (who allegedly was one of the prototype of the famous healing deity Wong Tai Sin 黃大仙), significantly contributed to the development and dissemination of Daoism there. Entering the Sui dynasty, the renowned Daoist Su Yuanlang 蘇元朗 arrived at the Qingxia Valley 青霞谷 of Mount Luofu to cultivate Daoist practices. He elucidated the concept of “dual cultivation of nature and life (性命雙修)” using the terminology of external alchemy 外丹 to explain internal alchemy 內丹, revitalizing the theory of internal alchemy and pioneering the trend of internal alchemy studies in the Tang and Song dynasties, exerting a profound influence on later Daoist developments. During the Tang dynasty, notable Daoist figures on Mount Luofu included Xuanyuan Ji 軒轅集, Shen Taizhi 申太芝, and Deng Yuanqi 鄧元起. In the Song dynasty, Mount Luofu continued to produce eminent Daoist scholars, such as Deng Shou’an 鄧守安, who had a close relationship with Su Dongpo 蘇東坡, as well as prominent “Southern School (南宗)” masters such as Shi Tai 石泰, Chen Nan 陳楠, Bai Yuchan 白玉蟾, and Peng Si 彭耜. Among them, Bai Yuchan studied the methods of the “Nine Tripod Golden Elixir (九鼎金丹)” with Chen Nan on Mount Luofu, later becoming one of the “Five

Ancestors (五祖)” of the Southern School of Daoism. The development of Daoism on Mount Luofu underwent significant transformations during the Ming and Qing dynasties. Previously associated with the “Lingbao Sect (靈寶派)”, in the late Ming and early Qing dynasties, the eleventh-generation successor of the “Quanzhen Longmen Sect (全真龍門派)” was appointed as the head of the five temples on Mount Luofu. During the Kangxi period 康熙, the Longmen Sect successor Du Yangdong 杜陽棟 assumed the position of head of the Chongxu Temple, establishing official regulations and transforming Mount Luofu into a sacred site of Daoism for the Longmen Sect. In the Daoist cosmology of “Grotto-Heavens and Blissful Lands (dongtian fudi 洞天福地)”, Mount Luofu is ranked seventh among the “Ten Major Grotto Heavens” and is referred to as the “Grotto-heaven of Vermillion Brightness Shining Truth (Zhuming yaozhen tian 朱明耀真天)”. Mount Luofu is not only a celestial abode for Daoist cultivation but also a sacred site for Buddhism. As early as 359 AD, the Dunhuang monk Shandao 單道 arrived at Mount Luofu to engage in spiritual practice, marking the beginning of Mount Luofu’s Buddhist history. According to the Official History of Guangdong (2007), by the end of the Jin Dynasty, approximately thirty Buddhist temples were built within the Guangdong region, with Panyu County 番禺 having the most, followed by Mount Luofu. Tang Dynasty was a flourishing period for the spread of Buddhism on Mount Luofu, during which eminent monks resided there, including Huaidi 懷迪 from Nanlou Monastery 南樓寺 who collaborated with Indian monks to translate the Lengyan Sutra 楞嚴經; the monk Yuanhui 元惠, who resided at Waterfall Rock 瀑布岩 and traveled between Mount Luofu and Mount Tiantai 天台山. In 738, Emperor Xuanzong 宣宗 built the Huashou Temple 華首寺 on the southwest foothills of Mount Luofu, where 500 monks congregated at its peaks. In the Song Dynasty, notable monks of Buddhism on Mount Luofu included Yunda 雲達, Qide 齊德, Shending 神定, and Zuyan 祖演. During the Ming Dynasty, numerous eminent monks emerged on Mount Luofu as well, including Zhikong 真空, Huiguo 晦果, Ruzheng 如正, and Shixu 十虛. Entering the Qing Dynasty, the monk Kongyin 空隱 and his disciples Hanshi 函是 and Hanke 函可 established the “Boshan Dharma Gate (博山法門)”. These esteemed Buddhist figures expounded Buddhist teachings on Mount Luofu, playing a significant role in spreading Buddhist culture in South China. In addition to the developments of local history and Daoist and Buddhist teachings, Mount Luofu is also one of the birthplaces of private education. Since the Jin Dynasty, many literati and scholars have established academies and study lounges on Mount Luofu, making it a popular place for study, gathering, and teaching, thus becoming an important local educational center. For example, during the Song and Yuan Dynasties, there were official institutions like the Yuzhang Academy 豫章書院, the Jingguan Academy 靜觀書院 in Huanglong Cave 黃龍洞, and privately established academies like the Zhangliu Academy 張留書院. In the Ming Dynasty, Mount Luofu witnessed the emergence of many private study halls and libraries, such as the Bitang Study Hall 弼唐精舍 and the Xianzi Reading Platform 洗子讀書台, along with the Four Sages Shrine 四賢祠 dedicated to venerable Confucian masters. Among the numerous eminent scholars who taught and received disciples on Mount Luofu, the most renowned was Zhan Ruoshui 湛若水, who held various high-ranking positions in the Ming government. Su Dongpo 蘇東坡 also resided on Mount Luofu for an extended period, during which he penned famous works like “Miscellaneous Notes on Mount Luofu (Zashu Luofushi 雜書羅浮事)” and “Inscription at the Zuoquan Pavilion (Shu Zhuoxiquan 書卓錫泉).” Additionally, notable literary figures such as Li Bai 李白, Du Fu 杜甫, Han Yu 韓愈, Yang Wanli 楊萬里, Liu Yuxi 劉禹錫, Zhu Xi 朱熹, Qu Dajun 屈大均, and Tang Xianzu 湯顯祖 have all composed poems and writings praising and memorizing Mount Luofu. Across its storied history, both locally and statewide, Mount Luofu has served as a hallowed ground of spiritual and intellectual practice, weaving together the tapestry of religious devotion and scholarly pursuit, creating a rich mosaic of cultural and intellectual expression and leaving an indelible mark on the cultural landscape of China.

Date Range: 200 BCE - 2024 CE

Region: Luofu Mountain, Huizhou city, Guangdong

Region tags: China

Area of Loufu Mountain in Huizhou city, Guangdong (present)

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Soymié, Michel. "Le Lo-feou chan: étude de géographie religieuse." *Bulletin de l'Ecole Française d'Extrême-Orient* 54 (1956): 1-132.
- Source 2: Chai, Mengyuan. 2022. "Idealizing a Daoist Grotto-Heaven: The Luofu Mountains in Luofu Yesheng 羅浮野乘" *Religions* 13, no. 11: 1043.
- Source 3: Goossaert, Vincent. "Luofu Shan." In *The Encyclopedia of Taoism*, edited by Fabrizio Pregadio, 722-723. Vol. 1. Oxford: Routledge, 2013.

Notes: Western language references regarding Luofu Shan are somewhat scarce; however, Soymié's paper stands out for its thorough and enlightening examination of Mount Luofu. Similarly, while Chai's study centers on a single text, it presents a sophisticated array of pictorial depictions showcasing the geographical panorama and historical evolution of Mount Luofu, complemented by an extensive bibliography.

- Source 1: Wang, Yiting 王逸婷. "Luofu shan dao jiao jing guan kong jian xing tai yan jiu" 羅浮山道教景觀空間形態研究. *Lingnan ligong daxue shuoshi xuewei lunwen* 華南理工大學碩士學位論文, 2021.
- Source 2: Chen, Guofei 陳國飛. "Cong xianshan dao yue yue: lingnan wenhua bantu zhong de luofu shan" 從仙山到粵岳：嶺南文化版圖中的羅浮山. *Guangxi shifan daxue shuoshi xuewei lunwen* 廣西師範大學碩士學位論文, 2016.
- Source 3: Huang, Min 黃敏. "Luofu shan yu lingnan wenhua" 羅浮山與嶺南文化. *She hui kexue jia* 社會科學家 no. 103 (2003): 156-160.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://en.daoinfo.org/wiki/Mt._Luofu
- Source 1 Description: The webpage offers an overview of Mount Luofu's significance in Daoism, detailing its history, religious practices, and architectural features, but it lacks in-depth coverage of certain aspects. Please check sources above.
- Source 2 URL: https://www.eco.gov.cn/news_info/50265.html
- Source 2 Description: This link is a brief introduction to Mount Luofu focusing on its present day developments as a tourist site.
- Source 3 URL: <https://zh.wikisource.org/wiki/欽定古今圖書集成/方輿彙編/山川典/羅浮山部#罗浮山>
- Source 3 Description: This link shows a list of writings and paintings starting from Song dynasty.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation
- Tree, grove, or forest
- Water source
- Cave

Type of elevation

- Mountain

Notes: Mount Luofu boasts 432 peaks, among which over 80 exceed an elevation of 1000 meters, with the main peak, Feiyun Peak, soaring to 1296 meters above sea level.

- Tree, grove, or forest
- Water source
- Cave

Notes: Mount Luofu contains over 980 cascading waterfalls, renowned springs, and 18 mystical caves. Within its rugged terrain lie 72 secluded grottoes and caverns, most of which are related to related practices.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

- Mound
- Leveling of ground
- Terracing
- Trackway or road-surface
- Water feature
- Plantings

Notes: Since the 1980s, the county government has assembled a team of domestic experts to formulate a comprehensive plan for the Mount Luofu Scenic Area, dividing the entire mountain into seven distinct zones. In 2004, Mount Luofu was designated as the fifth batch of National Key Scenic Spots by the State Council. Nowadays Mount Luofu is renowned for its well-developed tourism infrastructure and religious significance, featuring a network of roads and complete facilities. Among its prominent features are five Taoist temples— Chongxu Temple 衝

虛觀, Sulao Temple 酥醪觀, Huanglong Temple 黃龍觀, Jiutian Temple 九天觀, and Baihe Temple 白鶴觀 – forming an architectural ensemble representing Taoist heritage. Additionally, remnants of two other temples, Chashan Temple 茶山觀 and Hexian Temple 何仙觀, along with the Xihua Daoist Academy 西華道院, contribute to the mountain's religious significance. The site of Chashan Temple 茶山觀 lies within the Penglai Cave 蓬萊洞, marked by a preserved stone-carved gate, while the remains of Hexian Temple within the Shuilian Cave 水簾洞 feature a waterfall to the south.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Notes: The Mount Luofu Scenic Area is conveniently located, with distances of 35 kilometers from Boluo County 博羅縣, 51 kilometers from Huizhou City 惠州市, 70 kilometers from Dongguan City 東莞市, 90 kilometers from Guangzhou 廣州, and 100 kilometers from Shenzhen 深圳. Multiple expressways traverse the foot of the mountain, with dedicated exits providing direct access to Mount Luofu.

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– I don't know

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure
– Field doesn't know

↳ One single feature
– Water channel

↳ A group of structures:
– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– Yes

↳ A group of features:
– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– Yes

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
– Other [specify]: All answers above applied.

Notes: Mount Luofu serves a multifaceted role, encompassing various functions deeply rooted in religious, social, and cultural practices. At the heart of its significance lies its religious sanctuaries, notably the Taoist temples scattered across its slopes. Conceivably, various forms of rituals, prayers, and offerings are conducted to honor deities, seek guidance, and express reverence. Political authorities also exerted different levels of control over this area throughout history.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: As a local hub showcasing a blend of diverse religious beliefs and various human activities, most constructions and facilities on Mount Luofu have undergone a long history of modifications and reconstructions to withstand local and national challenges. For instance, during the late Qing Dynasty and into modern times, frequent military conflicts, such as activities of secret societies like the Tiandihui 天地會, resulted in damage to Taoist temples and shrines. The upheavals of the Republic of China era, the Japanese invasion of China, and the Cultural Revolution 文化大革命 further contributed to varying degrees of destruction to the Taoist landscape of Mount Luofu. Subsequently, intermittent periods of repair and reconstruction followed.

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

–Other [specify]: All applied

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–For religious reasons

–For political reasons

–As the result of war

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

–Other [specify]: Both

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: 朱灵芝

Notes: In the Taoist celestial hierarchy, many individuals who have attained mastery of the Tao are revered as deities. For instance, Zhu Lingzhi 朱灵芝, upon achieving enlightenment, ascended to become the immortal Zhu Zhenren 真人, presiding over Mount Luofu in Taoist tradition. Similarly, Ge Hong, after achieving transcendence, is venerated in Taoist scriptures and local legends. In the realm of Buddhism, Mount Luofu used to represent different sects and embrace diverse doctrines and practices, such as the Lotus Sutra and the Diamond Sutra, venerating different lineages and following distinct paths of spiritual cultivation.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– Yes

Notes: There exist official sites and local commemorations dedicated to figures like Ge Hong and other immortals, such as He Xiangu 何仙姑.

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

– Private individual

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Revealed by other kind of supernatural being(s) [specify]: Immortals

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Prodigy

Notes: The foundation myth of Mount Luofu involves the merging of two mythical mountains, Floating Mountain and Luo Mountain, during ancient times, symbolizing divine intervention and shaping the mountain's significance as a sacred site in Chinese folklore and religious traditions.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Notes: In the form of divine blessings, spiritual enlightenment, healing, or protection from the deities through different way of religious practices.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: While several Daoist figures authored religious texts and sacred doctrines on the mountain, Mount Luofu is extensively utilized for practical purposes such as spiritual learning and self-cultivation.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Mount Luofu serves as a prime example of Daoist "Grotto-heaven (dongtian 洞天)" belief and practice. During the time of Ge Hong, Daoist hermitages were established around Feiyun Peak in four directions. Chongxu Hermitage 衝虛庵 was situated in Zhu Ming Cave 朱明洞 to the south, Guqing Hermitage 孤青庵 was located in a flat area of Huanglong Cave 黃龍洞, Sulao Hermitage 酥醪庵 nestled in a stone cave below Baiyun Mountain 白云洞, and Baihe Hermitage 白鶴庵 positioned at the entrance of Zhu Ming Cave. After Ge Hong's era, Douxu Hermitage was renamed a Daoist shrine by Emperor An of Jin. Since the Tang Dynasty, Mount Luofu's Daoist landscape, focused on Ge Hong's hermitages and smaller surrounding temples, underwent extensive renovation and expansion, transitioning from hermitages to temples. Sulao Hermitage was officially reconstructed as Sulao Temple during the Tang Dynasty, while Guqing Hermitage became Tianhua Palace 天華宮 during the Southern Han period. Despite destruction during the late Qing Dynasty and modern times, reconstruction efforts have been made, particularly at the foothills' caves, surrounding Feiyun Peak alongside caves, stone inscriptions, and other scenic spots, presenting a distinctive architectural layout compared to the mythical Penglai Immortal Mountain 蓬萊仙山. Additionally, religious facilities and buildings have been occasionally built upon water, such as the famous Zhuoxi Fountain 卓錫泉.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The Taoist architectural complexes on Mount Luofu cover a large area and comprise various types of structures. These complexes are not only built around caves but also follow the natural contours of the mountain and water. They feature well-defined spaces including incense lanes, mountain gates, archways, pavilions, bridges, plazas, stairs, sculptures, and designed natural landscapes such as vegetation, stone carvings, waterfalls, and ponds. Additionally, these complexes have ceremonial spaces, mainly divided into two types: cloisters and courtyard gardens. The cloisters typically exhibit a symmetrical layout with the main hall as the axis, gradually rising in tiers, while the courtyard gardens are enclosed by the main shrines and side halls, forming internal courtyards, resembling the character "回 (hui)". These Taoist complex spaces consist of a series of individual building blocks arranged in a specific order and highlight the integration of natural beauty and architectural constructions.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: In most cases, the layout begins with the main hall dedicated to deity worship 祭祀神殿, surrounded by Linggong Palace 靈宮殿, Sanqing Hall 三清殿, and Shenxiao Hall 神霄殿. Folk gods, ancestral halls, temples for deities, such as Huang Daxian 黃大仙, Taiyi Hall 太乙, Eight Immortals Hall 八仙殿, and God of Wealth Temple 財神殿 follow in hierarchy. Functional spaces like dining halls and donation room fill in. The arrangement of worshipped deities from the main hall to the side halls also reflects a hierarchy from highest to lowest, with the Three Pure Ones 三清神仙 revered most and folk gods held in lower esteem.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and

Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
– I don't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:
Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.
– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:
– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Sand
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: I am not sure.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: concrete, glass, metal

Notes: Apart from the materials that are commonly used in traditional Chinese architecture and readily accessible in local natural regions, the current Taoist palaces on Mount Luofu incorporate human-made materials such as reinforced concrete, glass, and metal in their structures.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: Stone inscriptions, statues, incense burners, altars, lanterns, etc.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: Talismans, screens, murals, paintings, calligraphy, etc.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: I don't know.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– I don't know

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: I don't know.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– I don't know

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–Secco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: I don't know.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: I don't know.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– I don't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– I don't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Initially, the entire mountain wasn't designated for burial purposes. Over time, however, some renowned Daoist practitioners established their tombs there, becoming sites for reverence, including the cenotaph of Ge Hong.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):
– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human:
– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:
– I don't know

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:
– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– Yes

Notes: Throughout history, numerous small villages or human settlements have surrounded the complex.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: I don't know.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: On Mount Luofu, the veneration of The "Three Pure Ones (San Qing 三清)" and "Three Masters (三师, Sān Shī)" is central to Daoist practice. The Three Pure Ones represent the highest deities in Daoism, embodying the principles of origin, preservation, and transformation. Meanwhile, "The Three Masters," including Laozi 老子, Zhuangzi 莊子, and Zhang Daoling 張道陵, symbolize the diverse paths through which Daoist wisdom is conveyed. Additionally, Mount Luofu is home to a vast array of Daoist deities, ranging from abstract representations of the Dao to mythic cultural heroes and cosmic forces. These deities are ultimately viewed as emanations of the Dao and play significant roles in Daoist worship on the mountain.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:
– Yes

↳ Are they other:
–Other [specify]: I don't know.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– No

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– No

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Self-cultivation

Notes: The "Grotto-heaven" system symbolizes a pilgrimage where individuals traverse deep and secretive grottos, ultimately transcending from the earthly realm into a sacred domain. Most of the practitioners used the caves to meditate, practice, and endeavor to reach the other lands.

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– I don't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Ge Hong is the most obvious example. His wife, father-in-law, and some disciples are also venerated as human-divine immortals in later generations.

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

Notes: Daoist practitioners offer items like incense, fruits, rice, tea, flowers, candles, water, and monetary donations to deities as part of religious rituals to seek blessings and divine favor.

↳ Libations:

– Yes [specify]: Tea, liquor, purified water

↳ Offerings of food:

– Yes [specify]: Rice, fruits

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– No

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– Yes [specify]: Incense

↳ Daily life objects:

– Yes [specify]: Incense

Notes: Some practitioners will burn incense in their households occasionally to purify the space, invoke spiritual presence, and establish a connection between the earthly

realm and the divine realm.

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: I don't know.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: Purity is an important concept in Daoist belief in general.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: I don't know.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: I don't know.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: I don't know.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– I don't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– I don't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– I don't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Monetary offerings are sometimes made to support the upkeep of temples and the welfare of the clergy.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Incense, candles, etc.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– I don't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: I don't know.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– No

↳ By specific individuals

–Yes [specify]: Daoist masters and specialists often adhere to various sacrificial rituals, conducting special offerings on significant occasions or auspicious dates within the Daoist calendar. They also need to attend morning and evening scripture-recitation liturgies.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

- ↳ Is it required:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: I don't know.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

- ↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Birth
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Transition to adulthood
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Death

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: I don't know.

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

Notes: The architectural design and arrangement of temples demonstrate a deliberate organization for the orderly presentation of deities.

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:

– Yes

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– I don't know

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: I don't know the exact frequency.

Notes: There are several Daoist festivals celebrated on Mount Luofu, such as the birthday of "The Three Masters 三師," Double Ninth Festivals 重陽節.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

– Elites

– Non-elites

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: I don't know.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– I don't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

Notes: Fortune-telling is an ancient tradition and a popular practice in Daoist tradition. Personal information such as the lunar birthdate is provided to the priests to predict. There are fortune-telling services provided in the temples.

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– No

↳ Divination through human communication:

– Yes

↳ Is a human being the vehicle for the oracle:

– I don't know

↳ Is a human being the interpreter of the oracle:

– I don't know

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified sex/gender:

– I don't know

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified ethnicity:

– I don't know

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified class:

– I don't know

↳ Is sex-deprivation required:

– No

↳ Are intoxicants required:

– No

↳ Physical ordeal required:

– No

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:

– No

↳ Divination through non-living material:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: One of the most popular divination practices is known as "drawing a fortune stick (qiuqian 求籤)," where individuals seek guidance or answers by randomly selecting a numbered bamboo stick from a container filled with such sticks. Each stick corresponds to a specific divination poem or passage, offering insight or guidance on the seeker's question or situation. This practice is commonly carried out in temples or shrines dedicated to various deities or spiritual figures, often with the assistance of temple clerics or fortune-tellers who interpret the chosen divination for the seeker.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: "Finger calculation"

Notes: A method of fortune telling or divination where predictions or calculations about the future or the locations of objects are made by the movement of fingers and counting using the Daoist knowledge, revealing trends or providing answers.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– Yes

Notes: Healing in Daoism can be pursued through ritual practices, which might entail taking part in elaborate ceremonies with ritual petitions, or acquiring specific talismans (known as "fu 符") believed to possess healing properties.

↳ Cleansing

– Yes

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Medical treatment

Notes: Many Daoist experts are also skilled in traditional Chinese medicine as a result of practicing alchemy and may serve as medical helpers, offering remedies and treatments based on their knowledge of herbs, acupuncture, and other traditional healing practices.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: The long and profound history bears witness to the development of religion in southern China, with Daoism being predominant. Countless Daoist figures and followers have left their marks on the mountain. Among the most significant figures in the Daoist lineage of Mount Luofu are the following: Ge Hong 葛洪, who secluded himself on the mountain for cultivation and authored seminal works, laying the foundation for the Lingbao School 靈寶派 with his teachings on alchemy. In the Jin Dynasty, the focus shifted from external alchemy 外丹 to internal alchemy 內丹, with Su Yuanlang 蘇元朗 pioneering the path of inner cultivation, establishing the groundwork for later developments. During the Tang Dynasty, Xuanyuan Ji 軒轅集 was the most renowned Daoist on Mount Luofu, further developing the direction of internal alchemy, and laying the foundation for the flourishing of the Southern School 南宗 in the Song Dynasty. In the lineage of Daoist internal alchemy, Chen Nan 陳楠, and Bai Yuchan 白玉蟾 are revered as two of the Five Ancestors of the Southern School 五祖. After the transmission of Quanzhen Daoism 全真派 to the south during the Yuan Dynasty, it merged with the Southern School, and these two individuals were deeply rooted in Mount Luofu. The dissemination of Quanzhen Daoism experienced a period of dormancy due to several unsuccessful debates during the reigns of Emperor Xianzong 憲宗 and Emperor Shizu 世祖 of the Yuan Dynasty. Quanzhen Daoism was formally introduced to Mount Luofu in the 29th year of the Kangxi reign (1690) 康熙 by Du Yangdong 杜元棟, who propagated it at the Chongxu Temple 衝虛觀, the earliest temple to promote Quanzhen Daoism. He served as the head of the Chongxu Temple in 1698. Alongside him came Zhang Miaosheng 張妙生, who later became the founding patriarch of the Huanglong Temple 黃龍觀. After Du Yangdong, successive generations of Quanzhen Daoists Zeng Yiguan 曾一貫 entered Mount Luofu, becoming the head of the five major temples on the mountain.

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– I don't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– I don't know

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– I don't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: Many Daoist luminaries of Mount Luofu had direct connections with the aristocracy and government institutions of their time. For instance, during the Tang Dynasty, the imperial family revered Laozi as the Supreme Mysterious Emperor, and many Tang emperors sought longevity and immortality through Daoist practices. With the advocacy of the imperial court, Daoism flourished widely during the Tang Dynasty. There were numerous Daoist practitioners on Mount Luofu during the Tang Dynasty, some of whom had close ties with the imperial family and even participated in political activities. One of the prominent figures was Deng Yuanqi 鄧元起. It was quite common for them to receive financial support and render political services in return for their involvement in such interactions. Ordinary people or literati, in addition to practicing Taoist principles in their own lives, also regularly offer offerings and monetary donations to temples in order to receive more guidance and resources.

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– I don't know

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):
– I don't know

↳ Function for water management:
– I don't know

↳ Part of the transportation network:
– Yes

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: I don't know.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:
Economic documents, records etc.
– Yes

Are there scriptures associated with this place:
– I don't know